

This user manual is for the Standalone (no-PC) version. Build your OpenEvo first using the Assembly Manual.

Software Installation

1. Now we need to do a system test to make sure everything works. Let's first install the latest version of the Arduino IDE ([link here](#)). Next, we need to add the various libraries the robot will use. To do this, we need to go to the OpenEVO GitHub and download the latest code ([link here](#)). The repository may look different from the image below, but GitHub should still function the same way regardless of when it is accessed in the future. Follow the red arrows to download the Zip file containing all the OpenEVO data.

2. Once downloaded, extract the zip file into a convenient place. I use Windows and keep my files in an easy-to-find directory. Next, locate the folder containing the Arduino directory where your Arduino IDE was installed. On Windows, it's in the x86 Program Files directory. Once there, locate the Libraries folder. Copy all the zip files from the External Libraries folder of the OpenEVO GitHub folder into the Libraries folder of the Arduino Directory, as shown below. This will

allow the latest OpenEVO code to compile on your computer.

3. Open your Arduino IDE and then, while inside the IDE, open the easyEVOTypeD.ino project file from the GitHub directory you downloaded and unzipped. It will be located in the folder named easyEVOTypeD. Arduino requires the project file to be in a directory of the same name as the project file. Once you open the project file, the IDE will likely ask you to update the existing libraries. Feel free to do so, as it will not break compatibility (one would assume).

4. Next up, let's verify the code to make sure all the dependencies are present and that the code compiles properly. Plug a USB cable into the Arduino MEGA USB Port on the right-hand side of the OpenEVO robot. Plug the Power Adapter into your electrical outlet and connect

the adapter's barrel jack to the OpenEVO Power Port located at the back near the on/off switch. Flip the switch and plug in your OpenEVO's USB cable to your computer. Select the Arduino MEGA 2560 board from the board selection dropdown list as shown below.

5. Click the checkmark button on the upper right-hand side ("verify") and let the IDE do its thing. This will compile the code without uploading, which checks for syntax errors and any other mistakes one would make, so that when we upload it, it will not throw any errors. If this process was successful, you'll get a disappearing notification on the bottom right indicating the compilation was successful. Any errors thrown would be highlighted in orange font.

6. Upload the code to your OpenEVO using the rightward arrow button ("upload") on the top right side of the Arduino IDE. If all goes well, the Arduino IDE will display a disappearing notification indicating that the Upload is complete.

7. If the code worked, you should see the following screen, and the upload was successful. Yay, you did it! If the screen turns on and is backlit but no words appear, try turning the little contrast knob on the back of the LCD with a small screwdriver, as shown below.

If all went well, you should see this display on the screen.

Turbidostat Quick Setup

1. Let's start by assembling the reactor vessel. Gather the following parts:

- 1x Glass Vial
- 1x Magnetic Stir Bar
- 5x 60mm tubing
- 4x 2" 14 Gauge Needle
- 1x 4" 14 Gauge Needle
- 1x Silicone Reactor Cap

2. Connect one 60mm tube to each needle, ensuring the connection is tight. Slide the needles through the holes along the circumference of the silicone reactor cap.

3. Make sure the long needle's collar is just above the tops of the short needle collars, as shown below. We'll adjust the height of this needle later.

4. Place the magnetic stir bar in the glass vial and wrap the vial's mouth with aluminum foil. Wrap the silicone reactor cap assembly with aluminum foil, ensuring the needles do not tear the foil. This is important as the reactor cap needs to remain sterile.

5. Connect the 19cm cut silicone tubing to one end of the silicone media bottle cap. Wrap two of these media bottle cap assemblies with aluminum foil.

6. Wrap four 30cm female-to-female tubes in aluminum foil, ensuring the ends are covered with enough foil to fold over.

7. Autoclave the aluminum pouches and any media you wish to use. A typical turbidostat run uses the following:
 - 1000mL of bacterial media in a 1L Pyrex bottle (MEDIA BOTTLE)
 - Empty 1L Pyrex bottle (WASTE BOTTLE)
 - 250mL of distilled water in a 250mL Pyrex bottle (WASH BOTTLE)
 - 3x silicone bottle caps with 19cm media uptake tubing (you will need shorter tubing for a smaller WASH BOTTLE; measure enough tubing to touch the bottom of the bottle and cut it such that it floats just above the bottom)
 - 4x 30cm female-female silicone tubing
 - 1x Reactor Vessel Assembly
 - 7x Autoclaved [luer end caps](#)

8. Under aseptic conditions (dead air box or laminar flow hood), open the foil packet containing the media bottle caps and connect one to the 1L sterile pyrex bottle containing your media of interest (MEDIA BOTTLE), another silicone cap to an empty 1L sterile pyrex bottle (WASTE BOTTLE), and another silicone cap to a 250mL sterile pyrex bottle filled with sterile distilled water (WASH BOTTLE). Be careful not to touch the sterile surfaces of the media bottle cap and its uptake tubing. You can touch the part of the silicone cap that faces the outside world...just be careful.

9. Connect a 0.45 μm syringe filter to one of the outward-facing silicone cap connectors and a sterile luer end cap onto the other. Be sure to connect the air filter to the short connector and not the one attached to the media uptake tubing. I've made this mistake many times, so do be careful. Do this for all of the silicone bottle caps used (MEDIA, WASTE, and WASH bottles).

10. Unpack the autoclaved glass vial and reactor cap assembly. Into the glass vial, pour in exactly 50mL of your desired media. Be as precise as possible when dispensing this volume, as we will be adjusting the waste needle height based on this volume in the next step.

11. Adjust the long 4" needle's height such that it just barely touches the surface of the media volume. This height is critical because it defines the reactor's constant volume during turbidostat cycling.

12. To the luer connectors sticking out of the reactor vial assembly, place four LUER END CAPS and one LUER SYRINGE FILTER as shown below. I like to place the air filter adjacent to the long 4" waste needle, but this seems arbitrary.

13. To a 50mL tube, add one tablet of ef-Chlor NaDCC bleach (167mg version) and fill to the 45mL mark with distilled water. Allow the tablet to fully dissolve, vortex if necessary, and then top off to the 50mL mark with distilled water. This tube now contains 2000ppm of active chlorine, which we will use to surface sterilize the peristaltic pumps and thermometer needle. To a 15mL centrifuge tube, fill with this freshly prepared bleach solution, wipe the thermometer needle with 70% isopropanol, and place the needle in the bleach solution. If you wish to use conventional bleach, dilute standard household bleach with distilled water to prepare a 10% bleach solution, then process the thermometer needle as mentioned above.

14. Allow the thermometer to surface-sterilize for 20 minutes, then transfer it to a sterile 50mL tube containing sterile distilled water. This will wash off the excess bleach.

15. Carefully slide the thermometer needle into the center hole of the reactor cap assembly. Be sure not to touch the body of the needle with your hands. The reactor vial assembly is now complete.

16. Now, calibrate the pumps to ensure they dispense the correct amount of liquid. Unpack the autoclaved 30cm female-female tubing pouch and connect each port of the first two peristaltic pumps to the tubes (do this for each pump, with the pump-side tubing connected as shown in image 17 below). For each pump x , go to

'CALIBRATE PUMP x', then hit select. There are two tubes connected to pump x: Place one tube in water, and the other end in a graduated cylinder. On the OpenEvo, Hit select, and ensure that 10 dispensations correspond to roughly 10 mL, 1 mL per dispensation. Adjust the 'Motor Speed' parameter as necessary to achieve a correct volume (e.g., if 10 dispensations were less than 10 mL, increase the motor speed).

17. Using the remaining bleach, we'll use the PRIME PUMPS function to run bleach through the peristaltic pump tubing to surface-sterilize the lines. Connect each port of the first two peristaltic pumps to those tubes and route the other end into the 50mL tube containing our bleach solution, as shown below.

18. On the LCD faceplate of the robot, there are three buttons. The upper black one is the UP button, the middle blue is SELECT, and the bottom black one is DOWN. At the back of the robot, where the power line goes into the motherboard, there is a rocker switch. Flick the switch to the on position. The robot will initialize, and if all is well, there should be a screen showing one of the menu options, likely TURBIDOSTAT. Press the DOWN button to scroll through the menu until you reach the PRIME PUMPS function. Press the blue SELECT button to enter the PRIME PUMPS state. The robot will change its menu screen to look like the image below. The current pump should be the NEU or "NEUTRAL" pump (first pump on the left). The robot will now respond to your button presses, where the UP and DOWN buttons will activate the pump in that respective direction (press UP moves liquid from the right input line of the respective pump to the

left. You would press the UP button when you wish to suck liquid up from the reactor vial and into a media bottle. The DOWN button will push liquid from the left pump port to the right. The DOWN button would be used to push liquid from a media bottle into the reactor vial. The robot will only turn the pump that is indicated as the CURRENT PUMP. Let's make sure the selected pump is the NEU (neutral media; first pump on left). If the CURRENT PUMP is not NEU, press the blue SELECT button until the CURRENT PUMP is NEU as shown below. Press the DOWN button to command the pump to move 1mL of bleach from the bleach tube connected to the right pump port into the tubing. As the pump rotates, bleach will fill the left port tubing, pushing air out of that line and into the bleach tube. Continue to press and hold the DOWN button until all the air in the first pair of tubing is replaced with bleach.

19. Press the SELECT button to switch focus to the next pump (WST; second pump, left to right), then repeat attaching and priming the tubing with bleach until no air remains in all four tubing lines. Once all the lines are full of bleach, press and hold the blue SELECT button to exit out of the PRIME PUMPS state and return to the MAIN MENU.

20. Allow the bleach to surface sterilize the pumps for 20 minutes. While this happens, let's calibrate the stirring and optics of the robot! To do this, let's take apart the reactor base as shown below. The small rectangle with the two white wires is a 940nm LIGHT MODULE. This provides the illumination necessary for the OPTICAL DENSITY SENSOR (small rectangular module with red, black, green, and yellow wires). Be careful not to smudge fingerprints or scratch the sensor's face. To keep the sensor module safe, you can attach it magnetically to the 940nm LIGHT MODULE, as shown below. The magnets in each sensor bay module are oriented so that they bind to one another. This is a convenient way to protect sensors and lights from scratching.

21. Place the reactor vial assembly on the stirrer base, press the DOWN button to scroll down the menu until you reach the CALIBRATE STIRRING function. Press the blue SELECT button to enter the CALIBRATE STIRRING state. You will hear a faint humming sound indicating the stirring motor turned on. The robot will need at least five minutes to stabilize its stirring vortex, so just let it hang out for a bit. Once stable, measure the depth of the vortex cone relative to the tip of the thermometer needle. Press the UP and DOWN buttons to adjust the stirring speed, which will raise and lower the vortex cone tip with respect to the thermometer needle tip. My experiments suggest a vortex cone about 2mm from the tip of the thermometer needle (without overshooting during stirring) is a good stirring speed, which is reproducible. It's important that the vortex cone height is such that the tip of the thermometer needle remains covered with media at all times, the temperature measurement will be unstable and cause large fluctuations in media temperature during operation. Once you're satisfied with the stirring speed, press and hold the blue SELECT button to exit out of this state, which will automatically store the stirring speed value into the robot's config file (more on that later).

22. Reassemble the reactor base as it was before. The SENSOR BAY has four open slots. With the robot facing you, the left and right slots hold blank modules, which are place holders for later additions, the front module is the 940nm LIGHT MODULE, and the rear module is the OPTICAL DENSITY SENSOR. Once the robot is reassembled, return to the MAIN MENU by pressing and holding the blue SELECT button. Press the DOWN button to scroll down the main menu. Enter

the CALIBRATE OPTICS state, then adjust the LED brightness by long-pressing the UP and DOWN buttons until only the last digit of the IR SIGNAL value is constantly changing. The current configuration of the robot uses a specific light integration time that allows for the full dynamic range of the sensor, but to utilize this range, we need to adjust the LED brightness until it's just below the saturation point of the sensor. The maximum value of the sensor is 37,889, so raise or lower the intensity until you see only the last digit changing. If the last digit holds on an 8, then you're just above the maximum sensor reading. If you lower the light intensity a few more steps from this point, you should reach an intensity where the rightmost value of the IR SIGNAL is constantly fluctuating. Once satisfied, press and hold the blue SELECT button to exit out of this state, which will automatically store the LED power value to the robot's config file.

23. Let's return to the PRIME PUMPS function by pressing the DOWN button on the main menu and then pressing the blue SELECT button on the PRIME PUMPS function so we can purge the bleach out of the lines. Pull the first peristaltic pump's left-port tubing out of the bleach and connect it to the small 250mL bottle of sterile water, as

shown below.

24. Pull the first pump's right port tubing out of the bleach and connect it to the WASTE BOTTLE as shown in the image above. Select the NEU (first pump) on the PRIME PUMPS function and press the DOWN button to begin pushing out the bleach from the line, and replace it with sterile distilled water. Continue to press the DOWN button in 1mL increments until the entire line is free of bleach. An air pocket will travel through the tubing from the WASH BOTTLE through the pump and into the WASTE BOTTLE. I typically dispense until I see the air pocket travel into the WASTE BOTTLE, and I see liquid come out of the bottom of the WASTE BOTTLE's input line. Just to be safe, I pump out another 10mL of water by pressing the DOWN button ten times.

27. Disconnect the tubing attached to the WASTE BOTTLE and connect it to the short MEDIA NEEDLE across from the long WASTE NEEDLE. Do so quickly to not expose the tubing and needle openings for too long. The MEDIA BOTTLE is now connected to the reactor via the NEUTRAL PUMP (first pump on the left). Double check that the first pump's LEFT PORT goes to the MEDIA BOTTLE and the RIGHT PORT goes to the reactor assembly's MEDIA NEEDLE, which is across from the long WASTE NEEDLE.

28. Remove the second pump's LEFT PORT tubing from the bleach and connect it to the WASH BOTTLE. Remove the second pump's RIGHT PORT tubing from the bleach solution and connect it to the WASTE BOTTLE. Select the WST PUMP (second pump) in the PRIME PUMPS

function and press the DOWN button to push the bleach out of the tubing and into the WASTE BOTTLE. Repeat the dispensing until the bleach is fully out of the line as you did before.

29. Disconnect the WASTE BOTTLE tubing and connect that line to the long WASTE NEEDLE of the reactor assembly. Disconnect the WASH BOTTLE tubing and connect that line to the WASTE BOTTLE. Press UP while the WST (second pump) is selected to pull up any excess media from the reactor vial and purge the line of any liquid. **BE SURE TO PRESS UP, NOT DOWN.** Keep pressing UP repeatedly until the waste line is free of liquid. The OpenEVO is now primed and ready for TURBIDOSTAT mode. As one final pre-flight check, here is what lines need to be connected to which bottle and/or port:

MEDIA BOTTLE -> First Pump, Left Port

MEDIA NEEDLE -> First Pump, Right Port

WASTE BOTTLE -> Second Pump, Left Port

WASTE NEEDLE -> Second Pump, Right Port

30. Switch off the robot, press in the microSD card to remove it from the left side of the LCD screen, open the microSD card on your computer, and remove the "EEVO" file. This file will be automatically generated when we launch the turbidostat state later; now we just want to remove any prior data. Open the "config.txt" file in any text editor and modify the OD940 Upper and Lower bound variable to whatever your experiment requires. **BE SURE THE UPPER BOUND VARIABLE IS ALWAYS LARGER THAN THE LOWER BOUND.** Back up the config file just in case the microSD card ever becomes corrupted, and safely eject the card. Insert the microSD card back into its slot on the left side of the robot's LCD panel and turn on the robot.

● ● ● **CONFIG.TXT**

```
incubationSetpointTemp=30.00
OD940LEDBrightness=2460
motorStirringSpeed=84
pumpOneSpeed=1161
pumpTwoSpeed=1140
pumpThreeSpeed=1140
pumpFourSpeed=1160
END
```

31. Once the robot turns on and you see the main menu, press the blue SELECT button to enter the TURBIDOSTAT state. You will hear the hum of the stirrer turning on, and the screen should begin to display information, refreshing every second. The robot is now recording the optical density of the culture every second and will turn on the pumps when the culture reaches your upper OD trigger and continue to dilute in 1mL increments until it reaches your lower OD trigger. The value on the bottom right is the optical density of the culture, which will grow as the media becomes more turbid due to microbial growth. The top right denotes how many cycles of dilution have elapsed thus far, which you can monitor over time to determine the health of the culture or to know when you wish to end the experiment. Good luck and enjoy!

